

MINIMUM COLLISIONS ASSIGNMENT IN INTERDEPENDENT NETWORKED SYSTEMS VIA DEFECTIVE COLORINGS

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Abstract – In conjunction with the traffic overload of next-generation wireless communication and computer networks, their resource-constraint nature calls for effective methods to deal with the fundamental resource allocation problem. In this context, the Minimum Collisions Assignment (MCA) problem in an interdependent networked system refers to the assignment of a finite set of resources over the nodes of the network, such that the number of collisions, i.e., the number of interdependent nodes receiving the same resource, is minimized. Given the interdependent networked system’s organization in the form of a graph, there already exists a randomized algorithm that converges with high probability to an assignment of resources having zero collisions when the number of resources is larger than the maximum degree of the underlying graph. In this article, different from the prevailing literature, we investigate the case of a resource-constrained networked system, where the number of resources is less than or equal to the maximum degree of the underlying graph. We introduce two distributed, randomized algorithms that converge in a logarithmic number of rounds to an assignment of resources over the network for which every node has at most a certain number of collisions. The proposed algorithms apply to settings where the available resources at each node are equal to three and two, respectively, while they are executed in a fully distributed manner without requiring information exchange between the networked nodes.

Keywords – Graph coloring, Defective coloring, Games on graphs, Resource allocation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Next-generation communication and computer networks comprise an ecosystem of interconnected entities where multiple stakeholders and devices evolve in a physical, digital, or virtual space with others, resulting in interdependent interactions between them. Particular realizations of such systems include 6G subnetworks, Internet of Things (IoT) and sensor networks, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) and caching networks, and the intersection of these technologies with other disciplines, e.g., smart cities, industries [1, 2]. Although being part of a broader network infrastructure, emerging networked systems should be able to orchestrate and configure autonomously due to scalability, resilience, and security reasons, practically implying a loose interrelation among them regarding the information exchange. At the same time, though, these systems present competitive environments at their basis where the actions are not only interdependent but also conflicting. Therefore, effective methods to deal with the fundamental problem of resource allocation in a distributed manner while relying solely on local information are required.

In this article, following a graph-based representation and reasoning, we consider such an interdependent networked system and study the constrained resource al-

location problem with resource conflicts. The considered system is represented in the form of a finite graph, whose vertices and edges correspond to the networked nodes and their in-between dependencies, respectively, and which will be referred to as the *underlying graph* of the system. In this context, we are concerned with the problem of assigning a finite set of resources to the nodes of the network in such a way that the number of *collisions*, i.e., the number of pairs of interdependent nodes that are assigned the same resource, is minimized. The respective optimization problem is known as the *minimum collisions assignment* (henceforth MCA) problem. Targeting a solution that is applicable in a wide array of contexts, we equivalently consider the problem of assigning colors to the vertices of the underlying graph instead of assigning resources to the nodes of the network. Then, the MCA problem is translated as the problem of assigning a given number of colors over the vertices of the graph in such a way that the number of monochromatic edges is minimal. The aforementioned problem is known to be NP-hard (see [3]).

So far, the majority of the literature has focused on MCA problems for which the number of available colors (resources) is larger than the maximum degree of the underlying graph, and several algorithms have been proposed therein, both centralized and distributed, that

52 result in colorings of zero collisions. Nevertheless, it ap-
 53 pears that instances of the MCA problem with “few”,
 54 i.e., less than or equal to the maximum degree of the
 55 underlying graph, colors are much less investigated and,
 56 in this article, we aim to fill this gap. Respecting the
 57 need for distributed resource allocation, we capitalize
 58 on each networked node’s local awareness concerning its
 59 neighbors’ allocated resources and propose a distributed
 60 approach to the MCA problem in the case of there being
 61 “few” available colors. In the following, we refer to the
 62 potential entities/nodes of an interdependent networked
 63 system as players, and the set of resources as colors.

64 2. BASIC DEFINITIONS & PROBLEM FORMULATION

65 All graphs considered in this article are finite, without
 66 loops, and undirected. Throughout the article, given a
 67 positive integer k , we denote by $[k]$ the set $\{1, \dots, k\}$
 68 and, given a finite set F , we denote by $|F|$ its cardinal-
 69 ity. Given a graph $G = (V, E)$ and a vertex $v \in V$, we
 70 let $\mathcal{N}_G(v) = \{u \in V : (u, v) \in E\}$ be the *neighborhood* of
 71 v in G . The *degree* of v equals $\deg_G(v) = |\mathcal{N}_G(v)|$ and
 72 the maximum degree of vertices in G is denoted Δ_G . A
 73 k -*coloring* of G is a function $\chi : V \rightarrow [k]$. Given a k -
 74 coloring χ of a graph $G = (V, E)$, and a subset $A \subset V$,
 75 we denote by $\chi(A) := \bigcup_{v \in A} \{\chi(v)\}$ the set of colors of
 76 the vertices in A . Moreover, the *collision number* of χ
 77 is defined as $\mathcal{C}_G(\chi) = |\{e = (u, v) \in E : \chi(u) = \chi(v)\}|$,
 78 and the *collision number of a vertex* $v \in V$ under a k -
 79 coloring χ of G is defined as $\mathcal{C}_G(v; \chi) = |\{u \in \mathcal{N}_G(v) : \chi(u) = \chi(v)\}|$. In other words, $\mathcal{C}_G(\chi)$ equals the cardi-
 80 nality of the set consisting of all *monochromatic edges*
 81 of G under the coloring χ , and $\mathcal{C}_G(v; \chi)$ is the number
 82 of neighbors of v that receive the same color as v .
 83
 84

85 A k -coloring χ of $G = (V, E)$ is called *s-colliding* if
 86 $\mathcal{C}_G(\chi) \leq s$; it is called *d-defective* if $\mathcal{C}_G(v; \chi) \leq d$
 87 holds true for all $v \in V$. A 0-colliding coloring is
 88 referred to as a *proper coloring* in the literature. In
 89 other words, the MCA problem is a graph coloring prob-
 90 lem which is equivalent to the problem of determining
 91 $\mathcal{C}_k(G) := \min_{\chi} \mathcal{C}_G(\chi)$, where the minimum is over all
 92 k -colorings of G .

93 3. MOTIVATION & CONTRIBUTIONS

94 The application of the classical *Graph Coloring Problem*
 95 (GCP) in interdependent networked systems is particu-
 96 larly renowned for addressing the fundamental problem
 97 of channel allocation and sharing in wireless networks [4,
 98 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. The problem is translated into color-
 99 ing an interference graph where the vertices correspond
 100 to the network’s wireless links, and the colors are the
 101 channels. Seminal works, e.g., [4], have introduced dis-
 102 tributed greedy and randomized algorithms that target
 103 interference mitigation and throughput maximization in
 104

105 general-purpose wireless networks. Building upon these
 106 algorithms, channel allocation solutions to more special-
 107 ized network settings, e.g., Wireless Body Area Net-
 108 works (WBANs) [5] or 6G subnetworks [6], can be de-
 109 rived while more complex constraints can be taken into
 110 account after proper modification. A particular example
 111 can be found in [7] where the vertices belonging to the
 112 primary or the secondary network are allocated more or
 113 less spectrum, respectively, based on the cognitive radio
 114 principles in a network slicing setting. Going one step
 115 further in the complexity of considered resource allo-
 116 cation problem regarding the number of resources to be
 117 allocated, more recent works in [8, 9] study the joint Re-
 118 source Block (RB) allocation and power control in Full
 119 Duplex (FD) wireless networks using centralized greedy
 120 dual graph coloring algorithms. Other applications of
 121 graph coloring algorithms can also be found for content
 122 placement and caching in modern small-cell networks [9,
 123 10]. The vertices of the underlying graph correspond to
 124 the base stations where the files are cached, and, even-
 125 tually, the colors represent the files. The goal is to op-
 126 timize the content retrieval by the users and reduce the
 127 transmission time through the backhaul.

128 By exploring the related literature, it appears that the
 129 classical GCP algorithms find a wide application in re-
 130 source allocation problems in wireless networks. From
 131 a theoretical viewpoint, in the classical GCP, the objec-
 132 tive is to find the minimum positive integer k for which
 133 a given graph G on n vertices admits a 0-colliding k -
 134 coloring. This minimum value of k is referred to as the
 135 *chromatic number* of G , and is denoted $\text{chr}(G)$. The
 136 MCA problem is, in some sense, dual to the GCP. In
 137 the setting of the MCA problem, the parameter k is
 138 fixed and the objective is to find a k -coloring of a given
 139 graph G on n vertices that has minimum collision num-
 140 ber, among all k -colorings of G . Observe that when
 141 $k \geq \text{chr}(G)$ then the GCP implies that the MCA prob-
 142 lem admits a 0-colliding k -coloring. In particular, it is
 143 well known that when $k \geq \Delta_G + 1$ the graph G admits a
 144 0-colliding k -coloring, and one can obtain such a color-
 145 ing using a variety of algorithms, both centralized and
 146 distributed. It is also well known that when $k \geq \Delta_G + 1$,
 147 a 0-colliding coloring of G can be found in linear time
 148 by a centralized algorithm. However, the problem be-
 149 comes more delicate when the algorithm is required to
 150 be distributed. In this work, we shall be interested in
 151 distributed algorithms for the MCA problem.

152 Distributed algorithms for GCP are extensively ana-
 153 lyzed and discussed in [11], focusing on both determi-
 154 nistic and randomized instances. A representative ex-
 155 ample of a distributed deterministic algorithm for the
 156 GCP is presented in [12], managing to conclude a graph
 157 coloring in linear $O(\Delta_G)$ time. In particular, the work
 158 in [12] belongs to the broader category of graph col-
 159 oring algorithms that utilize an initial defective color-
 160 ing to conclude with zero collisions. Concerning the

161 distributed randomized algorithms, both works in [13]
 162 and [14] achieve to determine a 0-colliding coloring of
 163 a graph in $O(\log(n))$ rounds when the number of avail-
 164 able colors is at least $\Delta + 1$. However, they are lim-
 165 ited in that they require each player to communicate
 166 with her neighbors whether she has any conflict or not.
 167 The state-of-the-art behind distributed randomized algo-
 168 rithms can be found in [15], where an algorithmic
 169 complexity of $O(\log^3(\log(n)))$ rounds is achieved. Con-
 170 sidering the algorithm instances that do not require any
 171 communication between the players, preliminary work
 172 is provided in [16]. The respective algorithm yields a 0-
 173 colliding coloring of a graph in $O(\log(n))$ rounds when
 174 the number of colors available is at least $\Delta_G + 2$. The
 175 algorithm from [16] has been further improved in [3]
 176 to a distributed instance that yields a 0-colliding color-
 177 ing of a graph in at most $O(\Delta_G \cdot \log(n))$ rounds when
 178 the number of available colors is at least $\Delta_G + 1$, with
 179 the cost of requiring communication among neighbors.
 180 Another improvement of the algorithm in [16], which
 181 assumes no cooperation/communication among neigh-
 182 bors and which yields a 0-colliding coloring in $O(\log(n))$
 183 rounds when the number of available colors is at least
 184 $\Delta_G + 1$, can be found in [17]. In other words, when
 185 $k \geq \Delta_G + 1$, it holds $\mathcal{C}_G(k) = 0$, for any graph G .

186 In this article, we focus on instances of the MCA prob-
 187 lem for which $k \leq \Delta_G$ which, to the best of our knowl-
 188 edge, appear to be less investigated. One approach
 189 to the problem is to allow the possibility of leaving
 190 some vertices uncolored, and thus employ *incomplete*
 191 0-colliding k -colorings of the underlying graph (see [18]
 192 and references therein). Another approach is based on
 193 *dispersion games* (see [19] and [20]), but only applies to
 194 instances of the MCA problem for which the underlying
 195 graph is complete. Our approach is based on defective
 196 colorings (see [21]), and builds upon ideas from [16]. In
 197 particular, in [16], the authors define the *network color-*
 198 *ing game*, which is played on a graph G , and study the
 199 dynamics of the game when the players adopt a particu-
 200 lar greedy, randomized, strategy. It is shown, in [16],
 201 that the dynamics of the network coloring game under
 202 the aforementioned greedy strategy converge to a Nash
 203 equilibrium that gives rise to a 0-colliding k -coloring of
 204 G , provided that $k \geq \Delta_G + 2$.

205 In a conference version of this article (see [22]), we in-
 206 troduced the *defective coloring game* and studied its dy-
 207 namics when a particular greedy, randomized, strategy
 208 is adopted by the players. We demonstrated that the
 209 dynamics of this greedy strategy converge to a Nash
 210 equilibrium which also provides a defective coloring of
 211 the underlying graph. In this article, we improve upon
 212 the aforementioned greedy strategy. Our improvement
 213 is two-fold. On the one hand, we provide an improved
 214 version of the Greedy strategy, which is referred to as
 215 *frugal strategy*. The Frugal strategy allows for a reduc-
 216 tion of the number of available colors to each player

217 by one, thus being applicable to settings in which the
 218 Greedy strategy does not apply. In particular, the Fru-
 219 gal strategy applies when the number of available colors
 220 to each player is equal to 2. On the other hand, we
 221 improve slightly on the upper bound on the number of
 222 collisions, i.e., Corollary 1, from [22].

223 The remainder of this article is organized as follows. In
 224 Section 4, we state our main results and finding, which
 225 builds upon a game-theoretic model for defective graph
 226 coloring, and for which we propose the Greedy and Fru-
 227 gal, symmetric, randomized strategies for the players.
 228 This in turn results in two distributed randomized algo-
 229 rithms for the MCA problem. The detailed mathemati-
 230 cal analysis and proof of our main result are included in
 231 Section 5. In Section 6, numerical results obtained via
 232 modeling and simulation are presented to support our
 233 theoretical analysis, and Section 7 concludes the paper.

234 4. MAIN RESULT: DEFECTIVE COL- 235 ORING GAME

236 In this section, we define the *defective coloring game*,
 237 which has been introduced in [22] and may be seen as
 238 a variant of the *network coloring game* from [16]. Fix a
 239 graph $G = (V, E)$ having $n = |V|$ vertices and maximum
 240 degree Δ_G , as well as two integers k, d such that $k \in$
 241 $\{2, \dots, \Delta_G\}$ and $d \in [\Delta_G - 1]$. The defective coloring
 242 game on the graph G , denoted $DCG(G; k, d)$, is defined
 243 as follows.

244 The players of $DCG(G; k, d)$ are the vertices of G and
 245 participate in a game that is played over a number of
 246 rounds. In every round, all players simultaneously and
 247 individually choose a color from their set of available col-
 248 ors, which is assumed to be the set $[k]$. Thus, after round
 249 t , the choices of the players give rise to a k -coloring of
 250 G , which is denoted χ_t . The players of $DCG(G; k, d)$
 251 have only local information on the graph: they can only
 252 observe the colors chosen by their neighbors and are not
 253 allowed to communicate or cooperate. A player $v \in V$
 254 is said to be *happy* after round t if her collision number
 255 under χ_t is at most d ; i.e., when $\mathcal{C}_G(v; \chi_t) \leq d$. Oth-
 256 erwise, the player is *unhappy*. The payoff to a player
 257 in $DCG(G; k, d)$ is 1 when she is happy, and 0 when
 258 she is unhappy, and a configuration of colors for which
 259 every player receives payoff 1 is a *Nash equilibrium* of
 260 the $DCG(G; k, d)$ in the sense that no player has the
 261 incentive to unilaterally change strategy under such a
 262 configuration. Observe that, when the players have cho-
 263 sen colors that constitute a Nash equilibrium, the cor-
 264 responding k -coloring of the graph is d -defective.

265 The challenge is to find a *symmetric strategy*, i.e., a
 266 common strategy for all players in $DCG(G; k, d)$, that
 267 achieves to converge to a Nash equilibrium after a finite
 268 number of rounds using the available colors. Such a
 269 strategy has been proposed in [22], and is referred to as
 270 the *Greedy strategy*. Let $\chi_t(v)$ denote the color chosen

271 by player $v \in V$ after round t , and let $\chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v))$ be the
 272 set of colors chosen by the neighbors of v after round t .
 273 Then, the Greedy strategy is summarized as follows.

274 **Greedy strategy.** Suppose that $k = \Delta_G - s$ and
 275 $d = s + 2$, for some fixed $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 3\}$. As-
 276 sume further that each player in $DCG(G; k, d)$ adopts
 277 the following strategy: if a player v is happy after a
 278 certain round t , then she sticks to her choice in all sub-
 279 sequent rounds, i.e., $\chi_s(v) = \chi_t(v)$, for all $s > t$. If she
 280 is unhappy then in the next round she *changes* color,
 281 and chooses uniformly at random a color from the set
 282 $[k] \setminus \chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v))$.

283 In other words, under the Greedy strategy, a player who
 284 is unhappy after a certain round t chooses in the next
 285 round a color uniformly at random from the set consist-
 286 ing of those colors that are *not* chosen by her neighbors
 287 after round t . The corresponding algorithm is summa-
 288 rized in Algorithm 1.

289 **Remark 1.** Notice that, when the players of
 290 $DCG(G; k, d)$, with $k = \Delta_G - s$ and $d = s + 2$, adopt the
 291 Greedy strategy, a player who is happy after a certain
 292 round remains happy in all subsequent rounds. Further-
 293 more, if player v is unhappy after round t , then it holds
 294 $|[k] \setminus \chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v))| \geq 2$. In particular, an unhappy player
 295 has always at least two available colors to choose from
 296 in the next round.

297 Now, suppose that all players in $DCG(G; k, d)$ adopt
 298 the Greedy strategy. The main result from [22] reads as
 299 follows.

300 **Theorem 1.** Let G be a graph on n vertices and max-
 301 imum degree $\Delta_G \geq 3$. Let k, d be fixed positive inte-
 302 gers such that $k = \Delta_G - s$ and $d = s + 2$, for some
 303 $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 3\}$. Suppose that each player in
 304 $DCG(G; k, d)$ adopts the Greedy strategy. Then, for
 305 any starting assignment of colors to the vertices, the
 306 defective coloring game on G converges after at most
 307 $O(\log(\frac{n}{\delta}))$ rounds with probability at least $1 - \delta$.

308 In other words, when s does not depend on n and the
 309 players in the defective coloring game adopt the Greedy
 310 strategy, the game reaches a d -defective k -coloring of
 311 the graph in $O(\log(\frac{n}{\delta}))$ rounds with probability at least
 312 $1 - \delta$.

313 **Corollary 1.** Let G be a graph on $n = |V|$ vertices and
 314 maximum degree $\Delta_G \geq 3$. Suppose that $k = \Delta_G - s$,
 315 for some $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 3\}$. Then, it holds $\mathcal{C}_k(G) \leq$
 316 $\frac{n(s+2)}{2}$.

317 The proofs of Theorem 1 and Corollary 1 are analyti-
 318 cally presented in [22].

319 In this article, we show that a modification of the above-
 320 mentioned Greedy strategy provides an improved ver-
 321 sion of Theorem 1. The “modified Greedy strategy” is

Algorithm 1 Greedy strategy algorithm.

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1: An algorithm for each  $v \in V$  of the graph  $G =$ 
    $(V, E)$  of the interdependent networked system, hav-
   ing maximum degree  $\Delta_G$ , and a positive integer
    $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 3\}$ 
2:  $d \leftarrow s + 2$ 
3:  $k \leftarrow \Delta_G - s$ 
4: Choose  $\chi_1(v)$  randomly from the set  $[k]$ 
5:  $t \leftarrow 1$ 
6: while  $\mathcal{C}_G(v; \chi_t) \geq d + 1$  do
7:    $\mathcal{A}_t(v) \leftarrow [k] \setminus \chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v))$ 
8:   Choose a color  $\chi_{t+1}(v)$  uniformly at random from
   the set  $\mathcal{A}_t(v)$ 
9:    $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
10: end while
11: Return  $\chi_t(v)$ 

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Algorithm 2 Frugal strategy algorithm.

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1: An algorithm for each  $v \in V$  of the graph  $G =$ 
    $(V, E)$  of the interdependent networked system, hav-
   ing maximum degree  $\Delta_G$ , and a positive integer
    $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 2\}$ 
2:  $d \leftarrow s + 1$ 
3:  $k \leftarrow \Delta_G - s$ 
4: Choose  $\chi_1(v)$  randomly from the set  $[k]$ 
5:  $t \leftarrow 1$ 
6: while  $\mathcal{C}_G(v; \chi_t) \geq d + 1$  do
7:    $\mathcal{A}_t(v) \leftarrow [k] \setminus \chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v))$ 
8:    $\mathcal{B}_t(v) \leftarrow \{\chi_t(v)\} \cup \mathcal{A}_t(v)$ 
9:   Choose a color  $\chi_{t+1}(v)$  uniformly at random from
   the set  $\mathcal{A}_t(v)$ 
10:   $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
11: end while
12: Return  $\chi_t(v)$ 

```

322 referred to as a *Frugal strategy*, and is formally defined
 323 as follows.

324 **Frugal strategy.** Suppose that $k = \Delta_G - s$ and
 325 $d = s + 1$, for some fixed $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 2\}$. As-
 326 sume further that each player in $DCG(G; k, d)$ adopts
 327 the following strategy: if a player, say v , is happy after
 328 a certain round, say t , then she sticks to her choice in all
 329 subsequent rounds, i.e., $\chi_s(v) = \chi_t(v)$, for all $s > t$. If
 330 she is unhappy then in the next round she *changes* color,
 331 and chooses uniformly at random a color from the set
 332 $\{\chi_t(v)\} \cup ([k] \setminus \chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v)))$.

333 In other words, under the Frugal strategy, a player who
 334 is unhappy after round $t \geq 1$ chooses in the next round
 335 a color uniformly at random from the set consisting of
 336 her color choice after round t and the set of colors that
 337 are not chosen by her neighbors after round t . The cor-
 338 responding algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 2.

339 **Remark 2.** Notice that, when the players of
 340 $DCG(G; k, d)$, with $k = \Delta_G - s$ and $d = s + 1$, adopt the
 341 *Frugal strategy*, a player who is happy after a certain

342 round remains happy in all subsequent rounds. Further-
 343 more, if player v is unhappy after round t , then it holds
 344 $|\{\chi_t(v)\} \cup ([k] \setminus \chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v)))| \geq 2$. In particular, an un-
 345 happy player has always at least two available colors to
 346 choose from in the next round. Notice also that, in con-
 347 trast to the Greedy strategy, under the Frugal strategy,
 348 an unhappy player may not change color in the next
 349 round. Finally, observe that the Frugal strategy works
 350 when $k \geq 2$, in contrast to the Greedy strategy which
 351 requires at least three available colors.

352 Our main result implies that the conclusion of Theo-
 353 rem 1 remains unchanged when the players adopt the
 354 Frugal strategy.

355 **Theorem 2.** *Let G be a graph on n vertices and max-
 356 imum degree $\Delta_G \geq 2$. Let k, d be fixed positive inte-
 357 gers such that $k = \Delta_G - s$ and $d = s + 1$, for some
 358 $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 2\}$. Suppose that each player in
 359 $DCG(G; k, d)$ adopts the Frugal strategy. Then, for any
 360 starting assignment of colors to the vertices, the defective
 361 coloring game on G converges after at most $O(\log(\frac{n}{\delta}))$
 362 rounds with probability at least $1 - \delta$.*

363 In other words, when s does not depend on n and the
 364 players in the defective coloring game adopt the Frugal
 365 strategy, the game reaches a d -defective k -coloring of
 366 the graph in $O(\log(\frac{n}{\delta}))$ rounds with probability at least
 367 $1 - \delta$. Now, the number of monochromatic edges in
 368 such a coloring provides an upper bound on the quantity
 369 $\mathcal{C}_G(k)$, in the MCA Problem. In particular, Theorem 2
 370 yields the following.

371 **Corollary 2.** *Let G be a graph on $n = |V|$ vertices and
 372 maximum degree $\Delta_G \geq 2$. Suppose that $k = \Delta_G - s$,
 373 for some $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 2\}$. Then, it holds $\mathcal{C}_k(G) \leq$
 374 $\frac{n(s+1)}{2}$.*

375 *Proof.* Consider the defective-coloring game
 376 $DCG(G; k, d)$, where $d = s + 1$. From Theorem 2
 377 we know that, when the players in $DCG(G; k, d)$ adopt
 378 the Frugal strategy, the game reaches a Nash equilib-
 379 rium in $O(\log(n))$ expected number of rounds. Let χ
 380 be the k -coloring corresponding to a Nash equilibrium.
 381 In such an equilibrium point, all vertices are happy and
 382 the collision number of each vertex $v \in V$ is at most d .
 383 Let G_χ be the graph induced by the monochromatic
 384 edges of G under χ . Then, $\mathcal{C}_G(\chi)$ equals the number of
 385 edges in G_χ , and the result follows from the degree-sum
 386 formula in G_χ . \square

387 5. PROOF OF THEOREM 2

388 In this section, we prove Theorem 2. We fix a starting
 389 assignment of colors to the vertices, and we assume that
 390 each player in $DCG(G; k, d)$ adopts the Frugal strategy.
 391 Recall that we assume that $k = \Delta_G - s$ and $d = s + 1$, for
 392 some $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \Delta_G - 2\}$. We begin with a result that

393 provides a lower bound on the probability that a player,
 394 who is unhappy after round a certain round, receives
 395 “enough” available colors in the next round. This will
 396 require some additional piece of notation.

397 Recall that $\chi_t(v)$ denotes the color chosen by player v af-
 398 ter round t , and that $\chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v))$ is the set of colors chosen
 399 by its neighbors after round t . For each $t \geq 1$, let \mathcal{H}_t be
 400 the set of happy players after round t , and $\mathcal{U}_t = V \setminus \mathcal{H}_t$
 401 the set of unhappy players after round t ; hence, $v \in \mathcal{U}_t$
 402 means that $\mathcal{C}_G(v; \chi_t) \geq d + 1$. Given $v \in \mathcal{U}_t$, let
 403 $\mathcal{A}_t(v) := [k] \setminus \chi_t(\mathcal{N}(v))$ be the set consisting of those
 404 colors that are not chosen by her neighbors after round
 405 t , while $\mathcal{B}_t(v) := \{\chi_t(v)\} \cup \mathcal{A}_t(v)$ be the set of available
 406 colors to v after round t ; hence, under the Frugal strat-
 407 egy, player v chooses in the next round a color uniformly
 408 at random from the set $\mathcal{B}_t(v)$. Let $p_t(v) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_t(v)|}$ be the
 409 probability with which the unhappy player v chooses a
 410 color in the next round. For $v \in \mathcal{H}_t$, set $\mathcal{B}_t(v) = \{\chi_t(v)\}$
 411 and $p_t(v) = 1$. Similarly, given a vertex $v \in V$, let
 412 $\mathcal{H}_t(v) := \mathcal{H}_t \cap \mathcal{N}(v)$ denote the set of happy neighbors
 413 of v after round t , and let $\mathcal{F}_t(v) := \chi_t(\mathcal{H}_t(v))$ be the
 414 set of colors chosen by the happy neighbors of v after
 415 round t . Let also $\mathcal{U}_t(v) = \mathcal{N}(v) \setminus \mathcal{H}_t(v)$ denote the set
 416 consisting of the unhappy neighbors of v after round t .
 417 Observe that every color from the set $[k] \setminus \mathcal{F}_t(v)$ has
 418 a positive chance of not being chosen by the unhappy
 419 neighbors and therefore has a positive chance of belong-
 420 ing to the set $\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)$. Finally, let $f_t(v) = |\mathcal{F}_t(v)|$, and
 421 observe that, since happy players do not change their
 422 color, the sequence $\{f_t(v)\}_{t \geq 1}$ is non-decreasing. In par-
 423 ticular, this implies that for $z \geq 1$, $|\mathcal{A}_{t+z}(v)|$ is less than
 424 or equal to $k - f_t(v)$. The next lemma establishes a
 425 lower estimate on the probability that the number of
 426 colors that are not chosen by any unhappy neighbor of
 427 player $v \in \mathcal{U}_t$ after round $t + 1$ is at least $\frac{k - f_t(v)}{5^d}$.

428 **Lemma 1.** *For each $t \geq 1$ and each $v \in \mathcal{U}_t$, it holds*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)| \geq \frac{k - f_t(v)}{5^d}\right) \geq 1 - \frac{1 - 1/4^d}{1 - 1/5^d}.$$

429 *Proof.* Let $v \in \mathcal{U}_t$ be fixed and, for simplicity in nota-
 430 tion, let us set $f := f_t(v)$. Since v is unhappy, there
 431 are at least $d + 1$ vertices $u \in \mathcal{N}(v)$ such that $\chi_t(u) =$
 432 $\chi_t(v)$. We now proceed with estimating $\mathbb{E}(|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|)$
 433 from below; the proof is then completed by applying
 434 Markov’s inequality. As mentioned already, any color
 435 from the set $[k] \setminus \mathcal{F}_t(v)$ has a positive chance of be-
 436 longing to $\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)$. In particular, color $i \in [k] \setminus \mathcal{F}_t(v)$
 437 belongs to $\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)$ if it is not chosen by any neighbor
 438 $u \in \mathcal{U}_t(v)$ for which $i \in \mathcal{B}_t(u)$; this happens with proba-
 439 bility $\prod_{\{u \in \mathcal{U}_t(v) : i \in \mathcal{B}_t(u)\}} (1 - p_t(u))$. Therefore, denoting
 440 $E := \mathbb{E}(|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|)$, the arithmetic-geometric means in-
 441 equality implies that

$$\begin{aligned}
E &= \sum_{i \in [k] \setminus \mathcal{F}_t(v)} \prod_{\{u \in \mathcal{U}_t(v) : i \in \mathcal{B}_t(u)\}} (1 - p_t(u)) \\
&\geq (k - f) \cdot \left(\prod_{i \in [k] \setminus \mathcal{F}_t(v)} \prod_{\{u \in \mathcal{U}_t(v) : i \in \mathcal{B}_t(u)\}} (1 - p_t(u)) \right)^{\frac{1}{k-f}} \\
&\geq (k - f) \cdot \left(\prod_{u \in \mathcal{U}_t(v)} \prod_{i \in \mathcal{B}_t(u)} (1 - p_t(u)) \right)^{\frac{1}{k-f}} \\
&= (k - f) \cdot \left(\prod_{u \in \mathcal{U}_t(v)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_t(u)|} \right)^{|\mathcal{B}_t(u)|} \right)^{\frac{1}{k-f}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Recall that $|\mathcal{B}_t(u)| \geq 2$, for every $u \in \mathcal{U}_t(v)$. Since the sequence $\{(1 - \frac{1}{m})^m\}_{m \geq 2}$ is non-decreasing, it holds $(1 - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_t(u)|})^{|\mathcal{B}_t(u)|} \geq (1 - \frac{1}{2})^2 = \frac{1}{4}$. Summarizing the above, we have shown that $\mathbb{E}(|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|) \geq (k - f) \cdot (\frac{1}{4})^{\frac{|\mathcal{U}_t(v)|}{k-f}}$.

Now, since $k = \Delta_G - d + 1$, it holds $|\mathcal{U}_t(v)| \leq \Delta_G - f = k + d - 1 - f$, and hence, we have $\frac{|\mathcal{U}_t(v)|}{k-f} \leq d$. This implies that $(\frac{1}{4})^{\frac{|\mathcal{U}_t(v)|}{k-f}} \geq (\frac{1}{4})^d$ and therefore, it holds $\mathbb{E}(|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|) \geq \frac{k-f}{4^d}$. To finish the proof, let $X = k - f - |\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|$ and apply the previous lower bound on $\mathbb{E}(|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|)$ together with Markov's inequality to deduce $\mathbb{P}(|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)| < \frac{k-f}{5^d}) = \mathbb{P}(X > (k - f) \cdot (1 - \frac{1}{5^d})) < \frac{\mathbb{E}(X)}{(k-f) \cdot (1 - \frac{1}{5^d})} \leq \frac{1 - \frac{1}{4^d}}{1 - \frac{1}{5^d}}$, as desired. \square

The next lemma concerns a lower estimate of the probability that a player, who is unhappy after round t , becomes happy after two rounds.

Lemma 2. *It holds*

$$\mathbb{P}(v \in \mathcal{H}_{t+2} \mid v \in \mathcal{U}_t) \geq \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{5^d \cdot d} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1 - 1/4^d}{1 - 1/5^d}\right).$$

Proof. Let $v \in \mathcal{U}_t$. Player v will become happy after round $t + 2$ if she picks a color that has been chosen by at most d neighbors. However, it could be that the set $\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(v)$ contains a *bad color*, i.e., a color that has been chosen by at least $d + 1$ happy neighbors. Note that a bad color cannot make player v happy in any subsequent round. Therefore, to lower bound the probability that v is happy after round $t + 2$, we may exclude bad colors from the set $\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(v)$. In the worst case, all unhappy players have a bad color in their set of available colors. Let v be an unhappy player having a bad color in her palette. The bad color is $\chi_{t+1}(v)$. Now note that, conditional on $\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)$ and $v \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}$, the probability that player v is happy after

round $t + 2$ is greater than or equal to the probability that a fixed color from $\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(v) \setminus \{\chi_{t+1}(v)\}$ is chosen by at most d unhappy neighbors of v . Now, the probability that a fixed color $i \in \mathcal{B}_{t+1}(v) \setminus \{\chi_{t+1}(v)\}$ is chosen by at most d players $u \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v)$ is greater than or equal to the probability that color i is not chosen by any player from $\mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v)$; the latter probability being equal to $\prod_{\{u \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v) : i \in \mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)\}} (1 - p_{t+1}(u))$. To simplify notation, let us set $\pi(u) = 1 - p_{t+1}(u)$ and $b_u = |\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)|$, for each player u . Further, set $S_{t+1}(v) = \mathcal{B}_{t+1}(v) \setminus \{\chi_{t+1}(v)\}$.

Then, conditional on $\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)$ and $v \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}$, the probability that player v is happy after round $t + 2$ is at least

$$\begin{aligned}
P &:= \frac{1}{b_v} \sum_{i \in S_{t+1}(v)} \prod_{\{u \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v) : i \in \mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)\}} \pi(u) \\
&= \frac{b_v - 1}{b_v \cdot (b_v - 1)} \sum_{i \in S_{t+1}(v)} \prod_{\{u \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v) : i \in \mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)\}} \pi(u) \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2} \left(\prod_{i \in S_{t+1}(v)} \prod_{\{u \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v) : i \in \mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)\}} \pi(u) \right)^{\frac{1}{b_v - 1}} \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2} \left(\prod_{u \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v)} \prod_{i \in \mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)} \pi(u) \right)^{\frac{1}{b_v - 1}} \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \left(\prod_{u \in \mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)|} \right)^{|\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)|} \right)^{\frac{1}{|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|}},
\end{aligned}$$

where the first estimate follows from the arithmetic-geometric means inequality and the last equation follows from the fact that $|\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(v)| = |\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)| + 1$. As in the proof of Lemma 1, it holds $\left(1 - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)|}\right)^{|\mathcal{B}_{t+1}(u)|} \geq \frac{1}{4}$.

Therefore, we conclude that $P \geq \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{\frac{|\mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v)|}{|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|}}$. Now, observe that $|\mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v)| \leq \Delta_G - |\mathcal{H}_{t+1}(v)| = k + d - 1 - |\mathcal{H}_{t+1}(v)| \leq k + d - 1 - f_t(v)$, which implies that, conditional on the event that $|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)| \geq \frac{k-f_t(v)}{5^d}$, it holds $\frac{|\mathcal{U}_{t+1}(v)|}{|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)|} \leq 5^d \cdot \frac{k+d-1-f_t(v)}{k-f_t(v)} \leq 5^d \cdot d$. Hence, conditional on the event that $|\mathcal{A}_{t+1}(v)| \geq \frac{k-f_t(v)}{5^d}$, we have $P \geq \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{5^d \cdot d}$, and the result follows from Lemma 1. \square

We now proceed with the proof of Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 2. For a player $v \in V$, and a round t , let $Y_v(t)$ be random variables defined as follows:

$$Y_v(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \text{ if } \mathcal{C}_G(v; \chi_t) \geq d + 1 \\ 0 & , \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

501 From Lemma 2, we know that for every player v and
 502 any round t it holds $\mathbb{P}(Y_{t+2}(v) = 1 \mid Y_t(v) = 1) \leq 1 - c_d$,
 503 where $c_d = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\frac{1}{4})^{5^d \cdot d} \cdot (1 - \frac{1-1/4^d}{1-1/5^d})$.

504 Therefore, Lemma 2 implies that for any τ it holds

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_\tau &= \mathbb{P}(Y_v(2\tau) = 1 \mid Y_v(0) = 1) \\ &= \mathbb{P}\left(\bigcap_{i=1}^{\tau} Y_v(2i) = 1 \mid Y_v(0) = 1\right) \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^{\tau} \mathbb{P}(Y_v(2i) = 1 \mid Y_v(2i-2) = 1) \\ &\leq (1 - c_d)^\tau \end{aligned}$$

505 Plugging in $\tau = \frac{1}{c_d} \cdot \log(\frac{n}{\delta})$, we deduce that for every
 506 player v , it holds

$$\mathbb{P}(Y_v(2\tau) = 1 \mid Y_v(0) = 1) \leq \frac{\delta}{n}$$

507 Now, set $Y_t = \cup_{v \in V} \{Y_v(t) = 1\}$ for an arbitrary round
 508 t . The union bound then implies that

$$\mathbb{P}(Y_\tau = 0 \mid Y_0 = 1) \geq 1 - \delta,$$

509 as desired. \square

510 6. NUMERICAL EVALUATION

511 In this section, we evaluate the pure operation and per-
 512 formance of the Greedy and Frugal strategies in terms
 513 of the number of collisions at their convergence point
 514 and the required rounds until convergence is reached.
 515 To this end, different scenarios have been generated via
 516 modeling and simulation using the Erdős–Rényi ran-
 517 dom graph model $G(n, p)$ that captures the structure of
 518 any interdependent networked system in communication
 519 and computer networks. The parameter n corresponds
 520 to the number of vertices to be included in the randomly
 521 generated graph, while p is the probability with which
 522 an edge e between different vertices is created. In the
 523 following, we consider both different numbers of vertices
 524 n and probabilities p to provide a holistic view of the
 525 algorithms' operation. The numerical results have been
 526 averaged over 100 different random graph realizations
 527 under each specific graph setting.

528 First, we consider a fixed number of vertices, i.e., $n =$
 529 20 , and evaluate the concluding number of collisions and
 530 required rounds by varying the value of parameter s .
 531 Numerical results for both complete (i.e., $p = 1$) and not
 532 complete graphs with probability $p = 0.5$ are generated
 533 and averaged, presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The mean
 534 maximum degree of Erdős–Rényi graphs $G(20, 0.5)$ is
 535 $\Delta_G = 13$, resulting in $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, 10\}$ and $s \in$
 536 $\{0, 1, \dots, 11\}$ under the Greedy and Frugal strategies,
 537 respectively. Similarly, considering a mean maximum

Figure 1 – Number of collisions for different values of parameter s under the randomly generated Erdős–Rényi graphs (a) $G(20, 0.5)$ and (b) $G(20, 1)$.

538 degree $\Delta_G = 19$ for the Erdős–Rényi case $G(20, 1)$, the
 539 parameter s takes values from the set $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, 16\}$
 540 under the Greedy and $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, 17\}$ under the Frugal
 541 strategy, accordingly.

542 Fig. 1 depicts the number of collisions concluded in the
 543 aforementioned simulation scenarios. Apparently, an increas-
 544 ing value of the parameter s implies a lower number of
 545 available colors at each vertex and, thus, a higher number
 546 of collisions. The important conclusion driven from Fig. 1
 547 though is that, in this article, we have not only managed
 548 to devise a strategy that applies when the number of avail-
 549 able colors to each player is decreased to $k = 2$, contrary
 550 to the Greedy strategy proposed in [22] that is applica-
 551 ble when $k = 3$, but also the proposed Frugal strategy
 552 performs equally or outperforms the Greedy one in the
 553 majority of simulation scenarios in terms of the concluding
 554 number of collisions. The latter observation is more evi-
 555 dent in the complete graph case (Fig. 1b) and especially
 556 for large values of the parameter s . As the value of s
 557 increases, the number of available colors $k = \Delta_G - s$
 558 at each vertex decreases. Thus, including the color that
 559 made a player unhappy at her strategy set between subse-
 560 quent rounds, as suggested by the Frugal strategy, is an
 561 effective method that can even reduce the overall number
 562 of collisions in the graph. For the same value of the
 563 parameter s , this simulation scenario practically validates
 564 our theoretical findings following Corollary 1 and Corollary
 565 2 in that

(a)

(b)

Figure 2 – Number of rounds for different values of parameter s under the randomly generated Erdős–Rényi graphs (a) $G(20, 0.5)$ and (b) $G(20, 1)$.

566 the collision number at each vertex under the Frugal
567 strategy is lower than that under the Greedy.

568 Continuing with Fig. 2, the mean number of rounds of
569 the different players required under both Greedy and
570 Frugal strategies are presented for the (a) $G(20, 0.5)$
571 and (b) $G(20, 1)$ simulation scenarios and under vary-
572 ing values of s . We observe that as the value of s gets
573 bigger, the number of rounds required for the algorithms
574 to converge decreases owing to the vertices' threshold of
575 acceptable collisions that becomes looser, i.e., $d = s + 2$
576 under the Greedy strategy and $d = s + 1$ under the Fru-
577 gal strategy. Especially for small values of s , i.e., $s < 4$,
578 when the number of available colors is large, removing
579 the color that made a player unhappy at the previous
580 round from the available colors set, as suggested by the
581 Greedy strategy, allows for converging faster. For $s \geq 4$,
582 i.e., for a highly constrained color palette, the perfor-
583 mance of both strategies is equal, requiring on average
584 three rounds to converge.

585 Subsequently, we aim to assess the performance of the
586 Greedy and Frugal strategies under the randomly gener-
587 ated Erdős–Rényi graphs with probabilities $p = 0.5$ and
588 $p = 1$ and varying numbers of vertices $n = [20, 200]$.
589 For this purpose, we fix the value of the parameter s
590 equal to $s = 0$ (see results in Fig. 3) to examine the
591 algorithms' behavior when the number of available col-
592 ors $k = \Delta_G - s$ at each vertex is the maximum possi-

(a)

(b)

Figure 3 – Number of (a) collisions and (b) rounds for $s = 0$ and a varying number of vertices n under the randomly generated Erdős–Rényi graphs with $p = 0.5$ and $p = 1$.

593 ble. Fig. 3a further corroborates the fact that the Fru-
594 gal strategy concludes a lower number of collisions com-
595 pared to the Greedy one, while the gap between the two
596 strategies becomes wider as the number of vertices in the
597 generated graphs increases under both $p = 0.5$ and $p = 1$
598 cases. If we significantly increase the number of vertices
599 equal to $n = 200$, the performance improvement of the
600 Frugal strategy is almost double, yielding half the num-
601 ber of collisions under the Greedy strategy. Regarding
602 the mean number of rounds of the different players re-
603 quired for the algorithms to converge, the Greedy strat-
604 egy proves to be almost one round faster in the different
605 simulation scenarios (see Fig. 3b). As the number of
606 vertices increases, a small increase in the required num-
607 ber of rounds is observed while some minor variations
608 appear, especially under the Frugal strategy, which is
609 attributed to the randomized nature of the devised al-
610 gorithms in this article. Overall, the Frugal strategy
611 introduced in this article can be even double times bet-
612 ter in the number of collisions than our previous work,
613 with the cost of only one extra round when the available
614 colors at each vertex are equal to the maximum degree
615 of the underlying graph, i.e., for $s = 0$.

616 Last, it is interesting to investigate the operation of the
617 two strategies when the amount of colors available at
618 each vertex takes the lowest possible value, which hap-
619 pens when $s = \Delta_G - 3$ under the Greedy strategy and
620 $s = \Delta_G - 2$ under the Frugal strategy. The obtained

Figure 4 – Number of (a) collisions and (b) rounds for $s = \Delta_G - 3/s = \Delta_G - 2$ and a varying number of vertices n under the randomly generated Erdős–Rényi graphs with $p = 0.5$ and $p = 1$.

numerical results are presented in Fig. 4 for a varying number of vertices within the range $n = [20, 200]$ and Erdős–Rényi probabilities $p = 0.5$ and $p = 1$, respectively. In this simulation scenario, the two strategies operate identically, resulting in exactly the same number of collisions (see Fig. 4a) and the same number of rounds (see Fig. 4b) except for the Erdős–Rényi graph case with $p = 0.5$, where the players can conclude the game under lower than three rounds on average. The latter corroborates the observations driven from Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 for large values of the parameter s .

7. CONCLUSIONS

This article provided an extended and improved version of our previous work in [22] related to the Minimum Collisions Assignment (MCA) problem in interdependent networked systems with a constrained number of resources. We considered networked systems organized in the form of a graph, where the corresponding resource allocation problem can be equivalently translated as the assignment of a finite set of colors over the vertices of the graph such that the number of collisions of vertices that are assigned the same color is minimized. Being aligned with the needs of next-generation wireless communication and computer networks, e.g., scalability, resilience, and security, we adopted game-theoretic modeling and introduced distributed, randomized algorithms

that converge to a Nash equilibrium. The concluded Nash equilibrium, in turn, gave rise to a defective coloring of the underlying graph, i.e., a coloring according to which every vertex has at most a certain number of collisions. The Greedy strategy, which is our initial work, is applied in cases when the color palette of each vertex contains three colors. In this article, we built upon and improved the Greedy strategy to be applicable to cases where each vertex has only two available colors. The updated strategy was termed as Frugal. The estimated number of rounds required for the Frugal strategy to converge and the maximum expected number of collisions at each vertex were theoretically calculated and compared against the ones derived for the Greedy in [22]. Numerical results obtained via modeling and simulation were also presented that support our theoretical analyses. Overall, the Frugal strategy performed very closely to the Greedy one, providing an effective method to treat resource allocation problems with a significantly constrained number of resources, i.e., colors, that could not be addressed otherwise.

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